

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 20/05/2025

Accepted: 30/05/2025

Published: 16/06/2025

Citation: Terano HJR (2025) Assessing the Compliance of the Civil Engineering Program with the Philippine Technological Council's Accreditation Standards. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 18(22): 1801-1810. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v18i22.943>

* **Corresponding author.**

haroldterano@cspc.edu.ph

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2025 Terano. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.indjst.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Assessing the Compliance of the Civil Engineering Program with the Philippine Technological Council's Accreditation Standards

Harold Jan R Terano^{1*}¹ Camarines Sur Polytechnic Colleges, Philippines

Abstract

Objectives: The Philippine Technological Council – Washington Accord (PTC WA) provides internationally accepted standards for engineering education with an emphasis on outcomes-based learning and ensuring graduates are globally competent. This study investigated the perceived compliance of the Civil Engineering program at Camarines Sur Polytechnic Colleges with the nine PTC accreditation criteria. **Methods:** This study employed a survey method that gathers information on the level of compliance of the engineering programs along PTC accreditation standards. Likewise, documentary analysis was used to analyze the program profile and support the data gathered. Faculty members of civil engineering served as the study's respondents. They were requested to respond to the survey questions explicitly crafted to determine the level of compliance of the programs to PTC accreditation standards. **Findings:** The results show that the institution understands the significance of accreditation, but there are areas that need to be addressed. These are characterized by low scores obtained in the evaluation, which include the areas of student performance monitoring, faculty development, academic exchange, facilities, extension, industry linkages, and Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI). Findings also emphasized the importance of encouraging faculty members to pursue advanced studies and enhance the passing percentage in the licensure examinations of graduates. Based on these findings, the study formulated plans of action that will serve as a roadmap for the program's quest for PTC accreditation. **Novelty:** The developed plans of action aim to enhance the quality of the program, generate international recognition, and make graduates more competitive within the global engineering community.

Keywords: PTC; Accreditation; Civil engineering; Compliance; Washington Accord

1 Introduction

Globalization of economic activity is a reality that impacts engineering professionals and has changed the landscape of engineering undergraduate education⁽¹⁾. It has created a more competitive and interconnected environment, requiring engineers to possess global competencies to be effective in diverse cultural and demographic settings⁽²⁾. Likewise, the rising globalization of the workforce needs an awareness of the elements that influence professionals' decisions to work overseas⁽³⁾.

The quality of engineering graduates and professionals is vital in international practice. Providing quality education requires academic institutions to build cohesive systems that encourage strong partnerships among leadership, educators, industry stakeholders, government agencies, and local communities. Many institutions have also adopted internal and external quality assurance practices to continuously enhance their programs⁽⁴⁾. With the extreme mobility of students and faculty, there is a need for comparability of educational programs⁽⁵⁾. Ensuring the comparability of education remains a challenge, as it requires a suitable framework that can accurately assess and align the academic credentials of graduates from diverse institutions⁽⁴⁾. Currently, various frameworks exist to recognize engineering qualifications globally, such as the International Engineering Alliance including Dublin, Sydney, and Washington Accords. These agreements are designed to ensure that graduates from accredited programs possess the essential knowledge and competencies required to practice in engineering and related professions⁽⁶⁾. Each of these accords has its own criteria and guidelines for accreditation and its list of signatory countries. The graduates of accredited programs under these accords are recognized and eligible to practice their professions in signatory countries.

Historically, the quality of engineering education is controlled by the institution and monitored by national-level organizations⁽⁷⁾. However, the quality assurance and competitiveness of engineering education have been challenged. With the impact of globalization, educational institutions have been working to keep up with the present situation in the global arena.

Engineering educational institutions have been compelled to improve quality and standards by implementing quality assurance measures and program accreditation to ensure comparability and compatibility with similar programs worldwide. However, the quality of engineering graduates still varies significantly across countries, which poses challenges for engineers collaborating effectively in global, multidisciplinary teams⁽⁷⁾.

With this mismatch, the International Engineering Alliance resolved the issue in 1989. Six organizations from Australia, Canada, Ireland, New Zealand, the United Kingdom, and the United States signed an agreement known as the "Washington Accord". The Washington Accord (WA) is the engineering accord of the International Engineering Alliance (IEA) that focuses on accreditation professional engineering education programs. This is in contrast to the other accords: the Dublin Accord, which focuses on the accreditation of engineering technician education programs, and the Sydney Accord, which is on engineering technologist education programs⁽⁶⁾.

Washington Accord is a multinational agreement that recognizes substantial equivalency of engineering degree⁽⁸⁾. The agreement highlights two key principles: (1) graduates of accredited engineering programs should be mutually recognized as having met the academic qualifications for entry-level practice in any member country, and (2) accreditation by a member organization affirms that graduates are equipped for entry-level engineering practice. Over time, the Accord has expanded its membership, and as of 2023, includes 23 full members and 7 provisional members, collectively referred to as signatories. Full signatories of the Washington Accord have equal participation rights and mutually recognize each other's accredited qualifications as substantially equivalent within their respective jurisdictions⁽⁹⁾. Likewise, provisional signatories are recognized as having appropriate systems and processes to develop towards becoming full signatories.

The Washington Accord is closely based on the accreditation of the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET)⁽¹⁰⁾. Membership to the Accord requires countries to adopt similar set of criteria⁽¹⁰⁾. The ABET's criteria focused on an outcome-based approach and has been adopted since 2000. This model has influenced the design of various curricula across engineering programs around the world. These programs have integrated various elements into their curriculum to meet accreditation requirements.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) is the governing body responsible for overseeing higher education institutions in the Philippines. Through CHED Memorandum Order No. 46, series of 2012, the agency promotes a significant shift from a traditional, instruction-focused approach to one that is student-centered, emphasizing lifelong learning as a core principle. This paradigm shift calls for higher education demand to address the industry's present needs. The Technical Panel for Engineering and Technology (TPET) mandates all engineering programs to implement an outcomes-based education (OBE) system. This system allows engineering programs to align with international recognition standards, specifically through the Philippine Technological Council (PTC) and its Accreditation and Certification Board for Engineering and Technology (ACBET). The PTC sets specific accreditation criteria for engineering programs, which serve as the foundation for evaluating and making accreditation decisions on programs submitted by higher education institutions⁽¹¹⁾. The PTC facilitates the

recognition of engineering programs in accordance with the Washington Accord. The PTC-WA accreditation scheme could help higher education institutions (HEIs) offering engineering programs produce better-equipped and skillful technical men comparable to the engineers in the world⁽¹²⁾. By aligning programs with the Accord, institutions can enhance their prestige and become known globally. This recognition will be instrumental in promoting the global mobility of graduates and be recognized with the same rights and privileges as the Accord’s signatory countries.

This study aimed to determine the compliance of the civil engineering program to PTC accreditation standards. The program was assessed along with its compliance with PTC accreditation standards: Program Educational Objectives; Student Outcomes; Students; Faculty and Support Staff; Curriculum; Program Resources and Learning Environment; Leadership and Institutional Support; Program Linkages; Continuous Quality Improvement. Plan of actions were developed to further improve the compliance of the civil engineering program to PTC accreditation standards.

2 Methodology

This study employed a descriptive research method. Descriptive research is a method used to systematically describe existing phenomena by gathering data through instruments such as tests, questionnaires, interviews, or observations⁽¹³⁾. This study employed a survey method that gathers information on the level of compliance of the civil engineering program along PTC accreditation standards. Likewise, documentary analysis was used to analyze the program profile and support the data gathered.

Faculty members of the civil engineering program served as the study’s respondents. They were requested to respond to the survey questions explicitly crafted to determine the level of compliance of the programs to PTC accreditation standards.

A survey questionnaire was developed based on the standards set by the PTC and aligned with the nine criteria of the PTC Self-Study Report, which is part of the Certification and Accreditation System for Engineering Education (CASEE). The questionnaire utilized a 5-point Likert scale with the following interpretations: 4.50-5.00 (Very Adequate); 3.50-4.49 (Adequate); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Adequate); 1.50-2.49 (Inadequate); 1.00-1.49 (Very Inadequate).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Profile of the Program

The Civil Engineering program of Camarines Sur Polytechnic Colleges is under the College of Engineering and Architecture (CEA). It is one of the oldest engineering programs, along with the electrical, electronics, and mechanical engineering programs. The CEA is headed by a Dean, while the Civil Engineering program is headed by a program chair who oversees the planning, implementation, and continuous enhancement of the curriculum, instruction, and student outcomes.

The program is supported by a pool of qualified faculty members who not only handle instruction but are also actively engaged in research and extension services. These faculty members contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field through scholarly work while also participating in community outreach and development initiatives aligned with the institution’s mission. Over the years, the program has consistently produced board passers and graduates, including several topnotchers in the licensure examination. Presently, the program is Level IV accredited by the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities of the Philippines (AACUP).

Passing Percentage in the Licensure Examinations: Table 1 shows the school passing percentage of the licensure examinations for civil engineers from 2021 to 2024. The said examination is being conducted every April/May and November/December. There was no licensure examination in April/May 2021 due to the continued impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, which also led to the suspension of examinations throughout 2020.

Table 1. Average Passing Percentage

Year	April/May		November/December	
	School Passing	National Passing	School Passing	National Passing
2024	37.00%	39.27%	43.96%	37.07%
2023	46.03%	34.76%	48.44%	33.26%
2022	41.46%	42.35%	48.06%	39.34%
2021	-	-	19.35%	36.67%
Average	41.50%	38.79%	39.95%	36.59%

Source: *prc.gov.ph*

As shown in the table, the highest passing rate for the school was in April/May 2023, with a rate of 46.03%, compared to the national passing percentage of 34.76%. In April/May of 2024, the passing rate for the school dropped to 37.00%, while the national passing percentage is 39.27%. The three-year average passing percentage for the April/May licensure exams showed the school at 41.50% compared to the national average passing percentage of 38.79%. The performance of the school in the November/December licensure exams was consistent, with the school having its highest passing rate of 48.44% in 2023, which was considerably higher than the national passing percentage of 33.26% and its lowest in 2021 at 19.35%. The four-year average was 39.95% for the school, compared to a national average of 36.59%. The data indicates that the school generally met or exceeded national performance averages, most notably in the November/December period, and emphasizes the areas of strength and continued opportunity for improvement.

Number of Faculty Members: There are 16 faculty members. Seven (43.75%) of faculty members are permanent, while nine (56.25%) are on a contract of service (COS) status. This shows that the teaching force of the program relies majorly on the COS faculty. While COS faculty provide flexibility and bring industry experience, they are limited in function and involvement beyond teaching. To enhance academic quality, the institution may consider increasing the number of permanent faculty positions and providing COS faculty with support along with faculty development.

Educational Qualifications: Two (28.57%) of the permanent faculty have a doctorate, while five (71.43%) are master's degree holders. On the other hand, none of the COS faculty possessed a doctorate; two (22.22%) were master's degree holders, and seven (77.78%), were bachelor's degree holders. Data shows that permanent positions in state universities and colleges require one to have at least a master's degree. Likewise, this disparity in the level of educational qualifications means that the permanent faculty are more suited to handle courses, especially professional courses, perform instructional research, and effectively mentor students. The higher number of COS faculty who possess a bachelor's degree suggests that these faculty members may not be able to provide adequate academic depth. To enhance instructional effectiveness, it is suggested that COS faculty members be educated and trained through graduate programs, and this may be their opportunity to be granted permanent positions.

Number of Graduates: There were 646 graduates across five years (2020-2024). The graduation rates demonstrate a strong and consistent number of individuals graduating since 2020, especially in 2023 and 2024, when 161 and 160 graduates were recorded, respectively. While the number of 149 graduates in 2022 is lower, it is still clearly on an upward trajectory. There was a significant drop in graduates in 2021 to 51. This decline is attributed to the curriculum transition brought about by the implementation of the K-12 program in senior high school, which resulted in a two-year gap in student enrollment in college. The 51 graduates were the remaining students of the old curriculum before the full implementation of the new educational structure. In 2020, there were 125 graduates. This may possibly be due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the number of graduates has increased since 2022, which demonstrates the program's ability to adjust and maintain student completion rates compared to previous academic years.

3.2 Level of Compliance to PTC Accreditation Standards

The evaluation along Criterion 1 - Program Educational Objectives, indicates that the program has a clear and documented vision and mission; the PEOs are well-aligned with the vision and mission. This alignment ensures that the program maintains its strategic direction and relevance⁽¹⁴⁾. The visibility and accessibility of the PEOs suggest that there is a means of effective internal communication within the institution. However, the rating suggests that there is room for improvement in enhancing stakeholder engagement. The processes for the formulation, review, and deployment of PEOs are in place and function adequately, which indicates that the objectives remain responsive to the needs of the stakeholders.

The results under Criterion 2 - Student Outcomes, indicate an adequate implementation of student outcomes. This reflects that the program has a documented framework for aligning student outcomes to the educational objectives. The outcomes are well aligned with the PEOs, ensuring graduates are prepared for long-term professional success. The process of reviewing and updating student outcomes reflects a commitment to continuous improvement. The goal of continuous improvement is to improve student outcomes⁽¹⁵⁾. Performance indicators demonstrate that student progress is monitored, assessed, and evaluated. These performance indicators are necessary to meet the outcome and against which other performances can be compared⁽¹⁶⁾. Lastly, the student outcomes are communicated and disseminated to stakeholders. This promotes transparency and shared responsibility in achieving educational goals.

The results of the evaluation of Criterion 3 - Students indicates that the program has well-established policies, processes, and guidelines for supporting students. The admission, performance evaluation, advising, and graduation requirements are in place, documented, and implemented. The inclusion of student outcomes in evaluating performance shows that the academic assessments are aligned with learning goals⁽¹⁷⁾. Processes for monitoring progress and retaining students show that the program takes an active role in supporting student success. Policies on transfer credits, credit for work in lieu of courses, and transcript issuance are all in place and documented. This only reflects that there is transparency and consistency in academic operations.

However, academic exchange shows the lowest rating. This only suggests that the program needs further improvement in this area, which will provide broader learning opportunities to students. The results of the evaluation along Criteria 4 - Faculty and Support Staff show that the program maintains a strong and well-supported academic workforce. This also indicates that the faculty and staff are generally qualified and effective in engaging and supporting the program. The program has a competent and sufficient number of faculty members. Faculty involvement is essential for promoting student success and creating an inclusive learning environment⁽¹⁸⁾. The faculty workload shows variations in terms of the functions, which reflect a balanced distribution of the four-fold functions of instruction, research, extension, and production. The adequacy of faculty members in the program shows that their involvement in interactions with students, monitoring and assessing students, advising, and other activities are evident. There are available opportunities for professional development, although this area received one of the lower scores, suggesting that the institution may expand the training and research involvement of faculty members. The authority and responsibility of faculty members in program governance and management are strong, which shows that there is a collaborative and empowered academic environment. There is an evaluation method to determine the educational contributions of faculty members. However, this area got the lowest score, suggesting that the institution may further enhance its policy along with faculty development and promotion. The presence of support staff is in place, helping ensure that both teaching quality and operational support meet institutional standards⁽¹⁹⁾.

The evaluation of Criterion 5 - Curriculum reflects that the program has an organized implementation of the academic program. The program has an approved curriculum. This curriculum is supported by the study plan, prerequisite structure, and curriculum mapping process, which ensures coherence and alignment with educational outcomes. The alignment with PEOs shows that the curriculum is designed to prepare students not only to finish or complete the program but also for long-term professional success⁽²⁰⁾. Exposure of students to actual engineering setup and practice, including design experiences, industry-academe linkages such as On-the-Job Training (OJT) and laboratory course may help bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world applications. This may further enhance the problem-solving skills and prepare students for jobs in the engineering industry. Furthermore, quality education is further supported by sufficient teaching materials, such as books, syllabi, and samples of student work⁽²¹⁾.

The evaluation of Criterion 6 - Facilities and Learning Environment indicates that the program has adequate facilities and resources for student learning. The facilities, including offices, classrooms, and laboratories to facilitate the achievement of the PEOs and student outcomes are sufficient. The laboratory equipment and classrooms are sufficient. However, they received lower scores along upgrades and improvement which are necessary to ensure a productive learning environment.⁽²²⁾ The availability of computing resources includes an IT policy that ensures students' access to digital tools. There are also guidance and safety instructions for the use of laboratories and equipment. While there are policies for the maintenance and upgrading of facilities, they need to be strengthened to keep up with technological advancements and facilities that are relevant to the emerging trends in the industry. The library services and overall facility are rated well, indicating that the academic environment meets the needs of both students and facilities.

The evaluation of Criterion 7 - Leadership and Institutional Support indicates that the program is supported by adequate institutional framework. This suggests that the leadership and administrative systems sufficiently support the program's implementation. The institution, based on its approved organizational structure, involves all concerned individuals in planning and strategic decision-making. The program budget and financial resources support teaching, staffing, and infrastructure needs. The areas such as maintenance and upgrading of facilities and resources received slightly lower ratings, which suggests the need for an increase in funding and resource allocation. The staffing, which includes administrative and technical personnel, is considered sufficient. Faculty hiring and retention are functional. However, there needs to be an enhancement of the hiring process that will select the best for the position, an increase in funding, and additional hiring of qualified faculty members. The support for faculty professional development can be strengthened by providing opportunities for faculty members to attend professional training and pursue advanced studies aimed at enhancing instructional quality.

The evaluation of Criterion 8 - Extension Service, Community Service, and Industry-Academe Linkage shows that the program maintains engagement in the community and industry. The extension services offered include non-degree offerings such as short courses and technical training to support the professional development of engineers in the field and in the industry. The low score indicates that there is a need to broaden the services of the program along these services to increase industry impact and participation. Community-oriented programs are indicated in student activities. There are programs to assist the communities with social services to understand the impact of engineering solutions in the community⁽²³⁾. There is an active participation in the industry-academe linkage. However, the result reflects a need to further enhance the engagement of the program with the industry, including the involvement of industry stakeholders in curriculum planning and other academic activities to align the current professional practices and labor market needs⁽²⁴⁾.

The results of the evaluation of Criterion 9 - Continuous Quality Improvement reflect that there is a process for program evaluation and enhancement. Assessing student outcomes is well-implemented, and faculty members utilize data for evaluating students’ competencies. However, the evaluation of PEOs received relatively low ratings, suggesting that the process for assessing long-term graduate outcomes may be further enhanced. This could impact the program’s ability to ensure alignment with industry expectations and institutional. Likewise, the overall continuous improvement process received low ratings. This suggests that while data is being gathered, the use of this information for strategic enhancements may need to be more consistent or better documented. The presence of additional supporting documentation, such as minutes from evaluation meetings, indicates that actions based on assessment data are being recorded, which supports transparency and accountability.

To enrich the analysis and offer a broader perspective, the findings may be contextualized by referencing similar studies conducted among other state universities and colleges (SUCs) in the Philippines pursuing PTC-WA accreditation. For instance, a study conducted an evaluation across five SUCs in Western Visayas and found parallel outcomes—high levels of practice in curriculum delivery, student outcomes, and institutional leadership, but moderate levels in faculty training, extension services, and stakeholder involvement⁽²⁵⁾. This alignment of findings indicates that challenges in PTC compliance are not isolated but are shared across institutions, likely influenced by similar regulatory, resource, and policy environments within Philippine higher education.

Such comparative analysis underscores the value of cross-institutional benchmarking. By comparing institutional practices and performance with those of other HEIs pursuing the same accreditation goals, programs can identify scalable models of success and refine their approaches to better align with both national and international quality standards. This practice not only fosters collaborative learning but also strengthens the national capacity to meet global engineering education benchmarks.

3.3 Plans of Action

Tables 2- 10 outlines the targeted initiatives across the various criteria to strengthen the academic program’s quality, relevance, and responsiveness. Each action item is aligned with the institution’s mission and objectives, specifying clear goals, responsible units, timelines, and expected outcomes. These plans serve as a roadmap for the program for its quest for PTC accreditation.

Table 2. Plans of Action – Criterion 1. Program Educational Objectives

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Timeline	Expected Outcome
Conduct periodic stakeholder consultation forums	Ensure relevance and responsiveness of PEOs	Program Chair / CQAMS	Every 2 years	Updated, stakeholder-informed PEOs
Develop structured feedback mechanisms	Gather systematic input for PEO review	CQAMS	Within 1 year	Data-driven improvements
Institutionalize a regular review cycle	Standardize the review process	Curriculum Committee	Next academic year	Consistent evaluation and updating
Enhance dissemination of PEOs	Improve stakeholder awareness	Program Chair / Faculty	6 months	Greater visibility and engagement
Benchmark with other institutions	Align with national/international best practices	Dean/ Program Chair/ Faculty	Annually	Competitive and relevant PEOs

4 Conclusion

This study highlights the compliance of the civil engineering program with PTC accreditation standards. The results showed gaps in several areas. There is a common understanding of the significance of international accreditation, but there is room for improvement in aligning the programs with global standards. Some policy recommendations are made on the basis of the study’s findings. The institution should introduce regular professional development activities for faculty members to help them better comprehend the accreditation standards. Also, faculty members should be motivated and supported to pursue advanced studies and research opportunities in order to enhance their skills and contribute towards ongoing improvement in the curriculum. There should be systems of evaluation, including self and peer evaluation, to monitor and ensure compliance with the PTC accreditation standards. There should be a regular review of curricula with the participation of industry partners,

Table 3. Plans of Action – Criterion 2. Student Outcomes

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Timeline	Expected Outcome
Develop Outcome-Based Education (OBE) tracking tools	Monitor attainment of SOs effectively	CQAMS/ MICT	1 year	Reliable SO assessment reports
Conduct regular training for faculty on OBE	Strengthen capacity in outcomes-based assessment	L&D Committee	Every semester	Improved OBE-aligned instruction
Integrate SOs explicitly in course syllabi	Ensure SOs are addressed in instruction	Program Chair / Faculty	Each term	SO-aligned learning activities
Implement curriculum mapping	Link SOs to curriculum components	Curriculum Committee	Ongoing	Clear SO alignment across courses
Use tracer studies and employer feedback	Validate graduate performance on SOs	Alumni Affairs Office	Every 2 years	External validation of outcomes

Table 4. Plans of Action – Criterion 3. Students

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Timeline	Expected Outcome
Strengthen academic advising and mentoring	Support student success and retention	Program Chair/ Faculty	Ongoing	Improved academic performance
Enhance support for student organizations and leadership	Promote holistic development	OSAS/ Dean	Each academic year	Engaged and competent student leaders
Expand scholarship and financial aid opportunities	Increase access and equity	OSAS	Annually	Increased student retention
Establish a student feedback loop	Ensure students' concerns are addressed	CQAMS / Dean/ Program Chair	Every semester	Improved student satisfaction
Improve onboarding and orientation programs	Support transition to university life	OSAS/ Guidance Office	Start of each semester	Better adjustment and retention

Table 5. Plans of Action – Criterion 4. Faculty and Support Staff

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Time-line	Expected Outcome
Enhance Faculty Development Plans	Support career growth and teaching excellence	L&D Committee	Annually	Competent and motivated faculty
Improve faculty workload balance	Promote quality teaching, research, and extension	Program Chair/ Dean	Immediate	Better faculty performance
Enhance the conduct of regular performance evaluations	Identify strengths and areas for improvement	Dean/ Program Chair	Every semester	Data-driven staff development
Provide mentoring program for research and publication	Strengthen faculty capabilities in research writing and publishing	VPRIC/ RDSO	Ongoing	Increased research productivity and publication quality
Increase opportunities extension and production activities	Expand faculty involvement in community outreach and production initiatives	VPRIC/ ECSO/ PAXSO	Ongoing	Higher engagement and impact of extension and production
Hire qualified support staff and provide training	Enhance operational support for academics	HRMDU/ VPAA	Ongoing	Efficient program delivery support
Promote Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Research Projects	Foster innovation and cross-sectoral solutions	VPRIC/ RDSO/ Faculty	Ongoing	Broader research impact and collaboration

Table 6. Plans of Action – Criterion 5. Curriculum

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Timeline	Expected Outcome
Regularly review and update curriculum	Keep content relevant and current	Curriculum Committee	Every 3 years or as Needed	Market-aligned curriculum
Strengthen OBE implementation	Enhance learning outcome alignment	CQAMS/ Faculty	Ongoing	Effective outcomes-based instruction
Integrate emerging technologies and trends	Prepare students for future careers	Program Chair/ Faculty	Annually	Tech-savvy and industry-ready graduates
Increase industry-academe collaboration	Improve practicum and internship quality	CIRL/ Dean/ Program Chair/ OJT Coordinator	Each academic year	Relevant real-world experience
Establish faculty-student research collaboration	Enhance research culture, mentorship, and student engagement	VRPRIC/ RDSO	Annually	Joint research projects, student co-authorship, and research presentations
Conduct curriculum benchmarking	Align with national and global standards	Dean/ Program Chair/ Faculty	Every 3 years or as Needed	Competitive academic programs

Table 7. Plans of Action – Criterion 6. Facilities and Learning Resources

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Timeline	Expected Outcome
Conduct facilities audit and gap analysis	Identify needs and areas for improvement	CQAMS/ SPMU/ VPAA/ Dean	Annually	Prioritized facility upgrades
Upgrade laboratories, classrooms, and libraries	Provide conducive learning environments	CQAMS/ SPMU/ VPAA/ Dean	Ongoing	Modernized infrastructure
Increase digital learning resources	Support blended and online learning	LRD / ICTU	Annually	Improved access to learning tools
Improve internet connectivity and equipment	Enhance digital instruction capabilities	ICTU	Ongoing	Seamless tech-enhanced learning
Establish learning resource feedback systems	Monitor student satisfaction with facilities	CQAMS	Each semester	User-informed facility improvements

Table 8. Plans of Action – Criterion 7. Leadership and Governance

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Time-line	Expected Outcome
Promote transparent and participative governance	Strengthen institutional trust and collaboration	Top Management / CQAMS	Ongoing	Inclusive decision-making culture
Provide leadership training for academic heads	Improve management and academic leadership	HRMDU / L&D Committee	Annually	Competent educational leaders
Monitor effectiveness of policies and decisions	Evaluate governance performance	Top Management/ CQAMS	Yearly	Data-informed leadership actions
Enhance strategic planning processes	Align goals with stakeholder needs	IPDU	Every 5 years	Vision-aligned and stakeholder-driven plans
Institutionalize internal QA mechanisms	Sustain continuous improvement	CQAMS	Ongoing	Quality-informed decision-making

Table 9. Plans of Action – Criterion 8. Extension Services, Consultancy, and Linkages

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Time-line	Expected Outcome
Develop community engagement plans	Address societal needs effectively	ECSO/ Extension Coordinator	Annually	Impactful community programs
Document and evaluate extension projects	Ensure alignment and impact	ECSO/ Extension Coordinator	Every project cycle	Continuous improvement in outreach
Strengthen industry and alumni linkages	Promote collaboration and support	CIRL/ Dean/ Program Chair	Ongoing	Mutually beneficial partnerships
Encourage faculty and student involvement	Build civic responsibility	ECSO/ Extension Coordinator	Per semester	Active participation in outreach
Secure funding for extension initiatives	Sustain and scale community programs	ECSO/ Extension Coordinator	Each fiscal year	Resource-backed social projects
Strengthen research collaboration, partnerships and networking for enhanced extension and linkages initiatives	Promote collaboration, and research-based extension activities	RDSO/ Research Coordinator	Ongoing	Established partnerships, joint research-extension projects, and increased external linkages

Table 10. Plans of Action – Criterion 9. Continuous Quality Improvement

Action Item	Objective	Responsible Unit/Person	Timeline	Expected Outcome
Establish program-level CQI committees	Institutionalize improvement initiatives	CQAMS/ Dean/ Program Chair	Every academic year	Proactive CQI culture
Regularly analyze KPIs and metrics	Support evidence-based decisions	CQAMS/ IPDU/ Dean/ Program Chair	Quarterly	Data-driven enhancements
Conduct annual program self-assessments	Promote internal accountability	Dean/ Program Chair/ Faculty	Yearly	Identified gaps and solutions
Encourage participation in external accreditation	Validate quality externally	CQAMS	Every 3-5 years	Recognized academic excellence
Create CQI documentation systems	Track changes and improvement efforts	CQAMS	Ongoing	Institutional memory and transparency

accrediting agencies, and international universities. Industry-academic collaboration should be reinforced through policy with the new trends and requirements of the industry. Policies should be instituted to enhance research, extension, and academic engagement by promoting faculty-student research collaboration, strategic partnerships, institutional networking, and collaborative initiatives. These policies should also include a Research and Publication Mentoring Program to support faculty members in developing quality research and increasing publication outputs. Mechanisms for feedback should be created to capture inputs from employers, alumni, and students. To enhance the results of the licensure examination, the institution should improve the admission and retention policies by setting clear academic support systems and implementing a separate admission requirement and examinations for the engineering programs to ensure student readiness. A bridging program may be proposed to address gaps in foundational knowledge for incoming first-year students. A policy should be proposed focusing on review programs, practice exams, and mentorship for graduating students while aligning instructional strategies based on

an analysis of licensure exam performance data. A continuous quality improvement (CQI) system should be incorporated to assess and improve the programs on a regular basis. These policy recommendations can assist the programs in aligning with international standards, enhancing the quality of the programs, and improving the global competitiveness of the graduates.

5 Acknowledgement

Funding: The research was funded by Camarines Sur Polytechnic Colleges.

References

- 1) Ishchuk S, Sozansky L. National mechanical engineering in conditions of economic globalization. *Management and Production Engineering Review*. 2022;13(4):107–125. <https://doi.org/10.24425/mper.2022.142399>.
- 2) Ilyas M. Reflections on engineering education in the age of globalization. 2021. <https://dx.doi.org/10.18687/LEIRD2021.1.1.51>.
- 3) Guste RRA, Ong AKS, Diaz JFT, Cahigas MML, Gumasing MJJ. Exploring the desire of filipino engineering professionals to work abroad using the ECT-TPB theory. *Acta Psychologica*. 2025;255:104913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2025.104913>.
- 4) Almuhaideb AM, Saeed S. Fostering sustainable quality assurance practices in outcome-based education: lessons learned from ABET accreditation process of computing programs. *Sustainability*. 2020;12(20):1–26. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12208380>.
- 5) Demange G, Fenge R, Uebelmesser S. Competition in the quality of higher education: the impact of student mobility. *International Tax and Public Finance*. 2020;27:1224–1263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-020-09595-5>.
- 6) of Technology EI. International engineering alliance accords. Available from: <https://www.eit.edu.au/why-eit/accreditation/international-engineering-alliance-accords/>.
- 7) Ali MY, Ya'akub SR, Singh R, Hazza MHFA, Adesta EYT. Quality assurance in engineering education: accreditation and its global influence. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.46254/AN11.20211305>.
- 8) Ho J, Kortian V, Huda N, Lee A. Engineering management education: Washington Accord accreditation programs. *Engineering Management Journal*. 2024;36(4):353–365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10429247.2023.2285657>.
- 9) Alliance IE. Washington Accord. 2025. Available from: <https://www.ieagreements.org/accords/washington/signatories/>.
- 10) Agrawal A, Carroll J, Blackie M, Rosewell K, Pitterson N. Impact of curricula on student learning: a comparison of six chemical engineering programmes in three Washington Accord countries. *Southern Journal of Engineering Education*. 2024;3:1–25. <https://doi.org/10.15641/sjee.v3i1.1474>.
- 11) Council PT. Accreditation Criteria. 2019. Available from: <https://afeo.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/PTC-ADMISSION-OF-ENGINEERS-TO-ENGINEERING-PRACTICE-IN-THE-PHILIPPINES.pdf>.
- 12) Sarabia PS, Biray ET. Civil engineering program compliance of SUCs in western visayas to Philippine technological council – Washington Accord standards. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*. 2022;3(3):84–105. <https://doi.org/10.53378/352913>.
- 13) Muhajang T, Suryani Y. Implementation of 21st century learning through the stages of teaching at the right level approach for students of integrated islamic elementary schools. *Pedagonal Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*. 2024;8(1):47–56. <https://doi.org/10.55215/pedagonal.v8i1.9550>.
- 14) Carreño A. Strategic alignment in program management: A framework for sustainable business transformation. *Institute for Change Leadership and Business Transformation*. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922003>.
- 15) Garett MS, Mitrano S, Eisner R, Kochanek JR, Jones KT, Ibis M, et al. Continuous improvement in education settings: A literature review. 2021. American Institutes for Research [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.air.org/resource/report/continuous-improvement-education-settings-literature-review>.
- 16) Dimaano MR. Performance indicators as basis for students' performance improvement. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management and Sustainable Development*. 2023;11(2):104–115. Available from: <https://asiapjournals.org/performance-indicators-as-basis-for-students-performance-improvement/>.
- 17) for Engineering AB, Technology. Criteria for accrediting engineering programs. 2023. Available from: <https://www.abet.org/>.
- 18) Atobatele FA, Kpodo PC, Eke IO. Faculty engagement in international student success: a review of best practices and strategies. *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*. 2024;6(3):440–459. <https://doi.org/10.51594/ijarss.v6i3.968>.
- 19) Iqbal S, Moosa K, Taib CAB. Optimizing quality enhancement cells in higher education institutions: analyzing management support, quality infrastructure and staff training. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*. 2024;41(6):1572–1593. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-01-2021-0007>.
- 20) Terano HJR. Development of integrated curricula for the master of engineering programs using the CDIO Framework. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy*. 2019;9(3):44–55. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v9i3.10112>.
- 21) Haulle E, Kabelege E. Relevance and quality of textbooks used in primary education in Tanzania: A case of social studies textbooks. *Contemporary Education Dialogue*. 2021;18(1):12–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973184920962702>.
- 22) Nuevo EBT. Adequacy, utilization of laboratory equipment and performance of junior high school science teachers. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*. 2024;6(3):1–32. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i03.21166>.
- 23) Terano HR. The perceived impact of the community extension activities: A case of the electrical and electronics engineering programs in a state college in the Philippines. *Journal of Human Ecology*. 2023;82(1-3):8–15. <https://doi.org/10.31901/24566608.2023/82.1-3.3354>.
- 24) Shrivastava S, Bardoel EA, Djurkovic N, Rajendran D, Plueckhahn T. Co-creating curricula with industry partners: A case study. *The International Journal of Management Education*. 2022;20(2):1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2022.100646>.
- 25) Sarabia PES, Biray ET. Civil engineering program compliance of SUCs in Western Visayas to Philippine technological council. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*. 2022;3(3):84–105. <https://doi.org/10.53378/352913>.